

DETECTION OF CONTAMINANTS ON CFRP SURFACES – A NECESSITY FOR COMPOSITE REPAIR? ABSTRACT

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1 General Introduction

Composites are already used in aerospace for different applications, where they are confronted with different contamination scenarios under service conditions. Well known is the influence of humidity on the mechanical performance of composite structures. More difficult to determine and to forecast is the status of humidity of aircraft structures and the possible influence of humidity residues for adhesively bonded repairs. But humidity is only one contamination, which can alter the structural performance of composites itself and composite bonded structures.

Further contaminants of composites under service conditions are media like kerosene, hydraulic fluids, mineral oils, solvents, anti-icing fluids and aircraft washing agents. Even if most aircraft composites are based on epoxy resin systems, a general estimation of the behaviour of commercial epoxy based composites by the different contaminants is not possible. This is also one main reason that adhesively bonded structural repairs are not yet allowed by the airworthiness authorities EASA and FAA for load critical composite parts. Therefore, detection methods are needed for the assessment of the contamination source and for the degree of cleanliness of FRP adherends for bonded repairs. In principal different analytical methods are applicable like spectroscopy, ellipsometry, reflectometry, wetting tests and electronic noses.

2 Definition of Contaminants

Composites are influenced by different contaminants already during the manufacturing processes and afterwards under service conditions. In Table 1 the relevant FRP contaminants are summarized. The application of the testing methods described in section 3 refers to these contaminants, which can attack FRP structures during aircraft service life.

Contaminants	In or on laminate	Volatile (during curing)	Origin
Primer, Paint	On	No	Manufacturing
Release agents Hydrocarbons, Silicones, Fluorocarbons	On	No	Manufacturing Residues
Water	In	Yes	Manufacturing, Service
Kerosene	In/On	Yes	Service
Hydraulic Fluids Skydrol	In	Remaining Residues	Service
H-515 Oil Turbine Oil	In Mostly on On (?)	Remaining Residues No No (?)	Service
Methyl Ethyl Ketone	In	Yes	Service
Anti-Icing Fluid	Probably in	Yes?	Service
Runway de-icer	In?	Yes?	Service
Aircraft washing agent	?	?	Service

Table 1: Relevant FRP contaminants during manufacturing and aircraft service life. Highlighted in yellow are the 3 species, which have a high importance in the executed research projects.

3 Assessment of applicable detection methods

In this section, we focus on research results determined with Laser-Fluorescence [1], Infrared-Spectroscopy [2] and mainly with Electronic Noses [3].

All this three technologies fulfill important requirements, they are mobile detection methods and they are robust enough for the use under repair shop conditions.

3.1 Laser Fluorescence Detector

Fluorescence is the process of light emission from the substance to be measured, which is triggered by the absorption of exciting radiation. The fluorescence that is then emitted immediately after excitation of the molecule can be measured accurately even for very low concentrations [1].

Figure 1: Principal sketch showing the process of fluorescence emission [1]

The measurement principle is based on the time-integrated laser-induced fluorescence detection [LIF(t)]. An in-situ fluorescence signal is induced in the process medium through ultra-short laser light pulses and detected with a fast single photon-counting photomultiplier unit. Signal evaluation is

performed as intensity readings as well in transient analysis as a function of time (signal decay) [2].

The tested laser fluorescence detector is part of a process analyzer. Eight different positions on the CFRP surfaces were measured in a defined distance with a laser stimulation wave length of 266 nm. The test time of each measuring spot is on the order of seconds. The fluorescence signals of the samples were measured in the wavelength range of 300-400 nm. The test results are determined as relative fluorescence intensity counts, which were determined for hydraulic fluid and kerosene contaminated composite samples as well as for the reference samples. Differences in the relative fluorescence intensities between the CFRP samples are detectable. As shown in Figure 2, the residues of contaminants on the FRP surfaces are clearly detectable, variations in the “error bars” may be caused by the spatial resolution of contaminant inhomogeneity’s on the surface

Figure 2: Evaluation of relative fluorescence intensity of different contaminated CFRP samples in comparison with the reference sample [3].

3.2 FT-IR Detector

In the last years a lot of information has been published, concerning the use of FT-IR detection methods, for the detection of different contaminants on CFRP surfaces prior adhesive bonding. Infrared spectroscopy can be used to identify the status of chemical bonds on composite surfaces. The information can help to understand on one hand what chemical species are available for adhesive bonding and on the other hand what contaminants remain on the CFRP surface from manufacturing and aircraft service conditions.

Many results are based on the mid-infrared diffuse reflection techniques, which can indicate absorption changes in the M-IR range, caused by the different contaminants.

First publications dealt with the detection of heat damages on CFRP surfaces [4], [5], [6]. The results have shown that a CFRP material specific quantification of potential heat damages is possible.

Recent and ongoing investigation also start detection approaches for humidity, hydraulic fluids and contamination residues on CFRP surfaces.

Some investigations have already shown that a qualitative detection of humidity and hydraulic fluids on CFRP surfaces is already possible. The challenge will be now the quantitative detection. It seems possibly, when intelligent software programs are developed for the FT-IR technique.

Further on research studies have started [7,8,9] to evaluate Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy measurement methods as a potential technique to monitor surface CFRP contaminants coming from so called peel plies, release films or mold release agents. Such auxiliary materials, which are used in the CFRP production, remain contaminants like siloxanes, fluorocarbons and hydrocarbons on the CFRP surface. Because such contaminants can create unreliable adhesive bonds, the FT-IR techniques should also be possible to detect them prior bonding. Diffuse reflectance FT-IR technique show differences, but up to now they do not correlate the real amount of contaminants, like siloxane concentration. Further research is necessary to understand this behavior.

3.3. Electronic Nose Detector

In a research program sponsored by the German Federal Ministry of Economics and Technology [10], the suitability of so-called electronic noses was tested for the mentioned contaminants listed in Table 1. In this case the electronic nose consisted of a set of metal-oxide gas sensor arrays along with a humidity sensor. When gaseous contaminations are passing the sensors, they induce a change in their electrical resistance. The different responses of the metal-oxide sensors are evaluated via principle component analysis (PCA) [11]. With such a sensor array different contaminants on the FRP adherent surface can be qualitatively and quantitatively determined. The formation of gaseous contaminant species is generated by a specific heating device. The following figure 3 illustrates the principal application of electronic noses for the analysis on The FRP surface as well as for FRP milling dust for repair applications.

Figure 3: Principal application scenarios of an electronic nose detector, here in combination with an IR detector for the determination of CFRP contaminants, a) already during FRP milling; b) on the final milled surface [12].

For the electronic nose tests, the same two different epoxy laminates and three contaminants humidity, kerosene, and a hydraulic fluid (highlighted in Table 1) have been selected. Two probe sampling methods are possible: First, the dust generated during the FRP milling process may be analyzed. Second, contaminations species may be desorbed directly from the FRP surface.

3.3.1 Application for FRP milling dust

Here, particulate probes were collected during the milling process by suction of the milling dust through a filter pad. In a second step the filter pad with the particle dust on top was placed above the heating device. The contaminants are converted into the gas phase via thermal desorption, and the gaseous analytes are transported to the MOX sensor array for detection via a carrier gas stream. Figure 4 outlines this detection approach.

Figure 4: Electronic nose set up for the detection of CFRP milling dust

3.3.2 Application on the FRP surface

In this case a temperature controlled heating device will be placed directly on the FRP surface. Contaminants are thermally desorbed from the probe, and passed to the MOX sensor array similarly to the method outlined above. Figure 5 shows the layout of this detection system.

Figure 5: Electronic nose set up for the detection on the CFRP surface [12].

It could be experimentally demonstrated, that electronic noses are generally sensitive to a variety of different contaminants relevant for an aircraft service life. This was demonstrated first by placing a liquid contaminant droplet on the FRP surface, sampling in the surface method described above and analyzing the MOX responses. In a second step the artificially contaminated probes described above, along with the corresponding reference samples, were analyzed. Both milling dust and surface sampling methods were applied. In the following to figures experimental results are presented.

In figure 6 the responses of two sensors are plotted for the 4 contaminated probe types, using the surface desorption method. It can be seen that significant sensor responses are achieved. Due to the absorption of ambient humidity even in the reference sample, a basic humidity response is induced.

Figure 6: Responses of two different MOX sensors, tested on different contaminated epoxy laminates [13]

However, in the additional presence of the contaminants, the sensor responses are sufficiently different from the reference measurements, allowing for successful discrimination using PCA. This is demonstrated on the right side of figure 7, showing a plot of the three most significant principal components, clearly separating the four probe measurements..

Figure 7: PCA of the array responses for the four contaminants reference (red), humidity (green), kerosene (blue), and hydraulic fluid (teal).

4 Summary

The objective of the different analytical methods is the identification of potential contaminant species critical for the adhesive bonding and adhesive repair of fiber reinforced composites.

The three detection methods laser fluorescence, fourier transform infrared spectroscopy and electronic nose detection demonstrate their principal suitability. With such detection devices contaminations on the FRP surface can be already qualitative detected and identified. The next challenge is now the generation of quantitative contaminant values. If possible, than we could realize a big step forward in certification of contaminant-free FRP surfaces for safe adhesive bonding.

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